

Occurrence of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in Portugal

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In Portugal, irrigated rice—mostly cultivar Ringo—is planted on 32,000 ha. The 140,000 t annual production supplies about 2/3 the national consumption. No systematic survey of rice nematodes in the rice area had been conducted.

In 1980, we found specimens of *H. oryzae* (van Breda de Haan, 1902) Luc & Goodey, 1964 in soil samples collected in a vineyard established near a ricefield in central Portugal. In 1986-88, we undertook an exploratory survey covering the main rice-producing areas (see figure).

Ricefields at different sites were sampled at harvest or soon after and 30 root and soil samples per field collected. Each soil sample was composed

Location of ricefields surveyed for rice root nematode in Portugal, 1986-88. Solid circles = nematodes present, open circles = nematodes absent.

of three subsamples collected from around the rice roots, using a soil auger to 25-30 cm deep. Each root sample was composed of all the roots from two rice plants.

Parasitic nematodes were separated from the soil by sugar centrifugal flotation. For nematode extraction, undetached roots were washed free of soil and incubated in tap water for at least a week.

Male, female, and juvenile rice root nematodes whose morphometrics agree with those reported for *H. oryzae* were detected in 50% of the samples (see map). Nematode density ranged from 5 (3 females, 2 juveniles) to 30 (6 females, 3 males, 21 juveniles)/250 ml of soil and was as high as 31 (4 females, 1 male, 26 juveniles)/root sample.

This is the first record of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* in Portugal. None of the seven *Hirschmanniella* species known to attack rice has been reported in European ricefields. □

Population density of nematode *Pratylenchus zaei* at harvest and yield of upland rice UPLRi-5

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Population densities of more than 250 *P. zaei* per liter soil plus 1 g roots have been reported in upland ricefields in the Philippines and other Asian countries.

We studied the relationship between plant-parasitic nematode populations and yield of single hills of rice cultivar UPLRi-5 in an IRRI field naturally infested with *Aulosphora penetrans*, *Criconemella onoensis*, *Helicotylenchus* sp., *Pratylenchus zaei*, and *Tylenchorhynchus annulatus*.

Nematode population densities were determined in the rhizosphere and in the roots of 400 hills randomly selected at harvest. The weight of filled grains of each hill also was measured.

The weight of filled grains was correlated negatively with number of *P. zaei* detected per g roots or per liter soil plus 1 g roots (1 ls + 1 gr).

The table shows yield per hill after grouping the 400 hills into five classes based on population densities of *P. zaei*. Yield differences between hills supporting fewer than 50 *P. zaei* per 1 ls + 1 gr and those supporting 250 to 500 *P. zaei* was 14%; it was 16% between less than 50 and more than 500 *P. zaei* per 1 ls + 1 gr.

Because healthier host plants

Relation between population density of *Pratylenchus zaei* at harvest and average filled grain weight per hill of upland rice cultivar UPLRi-5.

Nematodes (no.)	Hills (no.)	Yield ^a (g)
0-50	77	4.4 a
50-100	54	4.3 abc
100-250	99	4.2 abc
250-500	79	3.8 bc
>500	91	3.7 bc

^a Average yield followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by t-test

support higher multiplication rates of plant-parasitic nematodes, yield is usually poorly correlated with nematode population density at harvest. It is better correlated with initial population density. Nevertheless, these results indicate substantial yield losses associated with *P. zaei* infestations in upland rice. The yield losses may be due to the nematode or to pathogens or stresses associated with the nematode. □

Farming systems

Legume residue incorporation and wetland rice yield

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Punjab soils are generally light in texture and have very low available N

and organic C. The hot and humid climate favors rapid decomposition of organic matter and losses of C and N. This limits the yield potential of rice, even with high rates of N fertilizer.

Incorporating plant material with a narrow C:N ratio could help improve rice yield potential. We studied the effect of incorporating mungbean *Phaseolus aureus* Pulse residue on yield of rice cultivars PR106 and PR108.

Soil of the experimental field was alkaline and low in organic C and available N. Mungbean per hectare was seeded at 25 kg/ha the last week of Apr.

In one treatment, 65-d-old pods were picked and the residue was removed. In the second treatment, the residue was plowed 1 d before transplanting 35-d-old rice seedlings. N was applied at 0, 90, 120, and 150 kg/ha in three equal splits: at transplanting and at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting.

Mungbean yielded 650 kg grain and 3 t residue/ha. The residue contained about 60 kg N/ha.

Rice yields increased with N application in both treatments (see figure). Residue incorporation conspicuously

increased yield. Grain yield with 120 kg N/ha plus residue incorporation was comparable to that with 150 kg N/ha and no residue incorporated.

Residue incorporation produced yields equal to those at higher N application with no residue. Incorporating residue increased rice yield 30% when no fertilizer N was applied, but the increase decreased with increasing fertilizer N (see table). □

Grain yield of 2 rice cultivars with applied N, with and without incorporation of mungbean residue. Ludhiana, India.

Increase (%) in rice yields with legume residue incorporation. Ludhiana, India.

N levels (kg/ha)	Increase (%) in rice yield	
	PR106	PR108
0	31.1	35.1
60	20.3	21.7
90	10.7	18.2
120	9.0	9.4
150	8.3	7.3

Performance of rice + maize intercropping in a drought-prone situation

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Yield and profitability of upland rice in Bangladesh is relatively low (average 1 t/ha) because existing local cultivars have low yield potential and drought is intermittent during vegetative and reproductive phases. The yield potential of maize is relatively higher than that of upland rice, and it has some drought resistance. But maize as the only crop in the early summer season is not culturally acceptable.

We studied the effect of intercropping maize with broadcast upland rice in a field trial Apr-Jul 1988. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with six replications. Rice (cv. Hashikalmi) was broadcast at 100 kg seed/ha and maize (cv. Barnali) was interplanted in rows. Treatments were 1.5-, 2.0-, and 2.5-m

row spacing for maize, 25 cm between rows.

In maize alone and maize + rice, fertilizer was applied at 100-26-33 kg NPK/ha. In rice alone, urea, triple superphosphate, muriate of potash at 40-26-33 kg NPK/ha was applied.

Intercropped rice yields decreased significantly with all maize row spacing; rice yield was highest with 2.5-m row spacing of maize (see table). Intercropped maize yields were not statistically different at all row spacings, but were

significantly lower than that of maize alone. Combined yield (expressed as rice equivalent) was highest in maize alone, followed by that in rice - maize intercropped at 1.5-m row spacing.

The land equivalent ratio was more than 1.0 in all intercropping arrangements; the highest was at 2.5-m row spacing of maize. Highest total energy produced was obtained with maize alone (0.81×10^7 cal/ha), followed by maize at 2.5-m row spacing (0.74×10^7 cal/ha). Gross return and benefit:cost

Yield and economic return of maize + rice intercropping at Manikganj, Bangladesh, Apr-Jul 1988.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Rice-equivalent yield (t/ha)	Land equivalent ratio	Energy equivalent ^b (10^7 cal/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
	Rice	Maize					
Rice alone	1.1 a	-	1.1	1.0	.40	174	1.25
Maize alone	-	2.3 a	2.3	1.0	.81	363	1.52
Rice + maize (1.5 × 0.25 m)	0.6 b	1.5 b	2.1	1.10	.64	329	1.34
Rice + maize (12.0 × 0.5 m)	0.6 b	1.4 b	2.0	1.14	.70	311	1.27
Rice + maize (2.5 × 0.5 m)	0.7 b	1.4 b	2.1	1.27	.74	326	1.35
CV (%)	14.6	6.7	-	-	-	-	-

^aIn a column under each condition, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bCaloric values for rice and maize were calculated as 360 and 349 calories/100g, respectively, considering 66% and 100% edible yield of unhusked rice and maize, respectively.